

Isospectral Hulthen ´ Potential

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Abstract : Supersymmetric Quantum Mechanics is an interesting framework to analyze nonrelativistic quantal problems. Using these techniques, we construct a family of strictly isospectral Hulthen potentials. Isospectral wave functions are generated and plotted for different values of the deformation parameter.

Keywords : Hulthen potential, Isospectral Hamiltonian

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014